

Shannon's Entropy and the Correspondence Principle

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In the literature (e.g. (1)), the expression $-\text{density}(x) \ln(\text{density}(x))$ is used as Shannon's spatial entropy for a quantum system (bound or not). For the bound case, the correspondence principle is said to hold for high energy levels (2). In that case, quantum density $= W(x)W(x)$ ($W(x)$ =real wavefunction) is said to be equivalent to the classical density $C/v(x)$ where $v(x)$ the velocity is given by $.5mv(x)v(x) + V(x) = E$. Classical density yields a curve which passes through peak regions of quantum density humps. In the classical case, particle motion is completely determinate. $C/v(x)$ as a density (probability) is proportional to dt , the amount of time a particle spends passing through a fixed length dx . If the particle moves quickly, it spends little time, and hence there is less time for a measurement (i.e one may miss the particle due to its speed). We argue in this note that such a scenario does not seem to be in keeping with the ideas of Shannon's entropy where one has probabilities for certain mutually exclusive events at each t_i . For example at each t_i , one may toss a coin. If it is not "heads", this means it is tails. For the classical particle in the correspondence principle, each dx region has its own probability proportional to $dt = dx/v(x)$. Thus, each dx is a region of its own in terms of probability. Thus, if C_i measurements of the presence of the particle are made within dx of x_i out of N trials, the probability that a measurement is made in dx at x_i is C_i/N and the probability that it is not is $1-C_i/N$. Thus, unlike Shannon's picture, various arrangements do not have the same weight or probability. We investigate this scenario in more detail and argue that it does not follow the approach of Shannon's entropy. We also try to connect with the quantum situation.

Shannon's Entropy

Shannon's entropy is given by $-\text{Sum over } i \text{ } P_i \ln(P_i)$, where P_i is the probability for outcome i to occur in a particular trial at time t_j . For example, if one tosses a coin at t_j , P_1 =probability for heads and P_2 =probability for tails. Thus, it makes sense to normalize $P_1+P_2=1$ because one either has heads or tails at t_j . This may be extended to systems where there are more outcomes than two. If one has numerous trials i.e. N t_j values, one expects an outcome i to occur $N P_i$ times to high accuracy. The probability for a particular set of N t_j results is then:

Probability for a single set of N t_j results = $\text{Product } i \text{ } P_i^{N P_i}$

Or $\ln(\text{Prob}) = \text{Sum over } i \text{ } N P_i \ln(P_i)$ ((1))

((1)) implies that $1/\text{Number of arrangements}$ should also yield the same probability. The \ln of the number of arrangements is:

$\ln\{N! / \text{Product over } i \text{ } N P_i\} = N \ln(N) - \text{Sum } N P_i \ln(P_i)$ ((2))

((2)) matches ((1)) and each arrangement carries the same probability or weight.

In a later section, we apply these ideas to a classical density and see that they do not hold, but first we wish to discuss quantum spatial density.

Quantum Spatial Density

For a bound state, quantum spatial density is $W(x)W(x)$. We argue the quantum bound system involves stochastic hits from a potential $V(x) = \sum_k V(k) \exp(ikx)$, i.e. the potential is only $V(x)$ on average and particle motion is stochastic. A momentum distribution is established at each x with a conditional probability $P(p/x) = a(p) \exp(ipx) / W(x)$. The distribution must yield an average kinetic energy $\sum_p p^2 / 2m P(p/x)$ equivalent to the classical kinetic energy at x . $P(p/x)$ is related to the wavefunction, but does not directly describe individual particle motion. Because the average kinetic energy changes at each point, the momentum probability density must change, thus there is x probability in the problem. A particle at x with momentum p_1 receives a stochastic hit changing to p_2 . The relative probability is approximated by: $a(p_1) \exp(ip_1 x) / a(p_2) \exp(ip_2 x)$. Summing yields the spatial quantum density, which includes both forward and backward motion which leads to cancellation among $\sin(px)$ type terms i.e. interference. We argue $W(x)$ is a statistical average and so also the density. The wavefunction ensures the average kinetic energy at x and $x+dx$ changes just as the classical kinetic energy and so it seems to capture average motion from x to $x+dx$. Given that one has stochastic momentum hits at x , it is possible for a particle to receive a very large hit and arrive far from x in a time dt , but this applies to single particle motion, not to the average $W(x)$. For the average $W(x)$, it seems unusual to consider independent motion from x with $P(x)$ to x_i with $P(x_i)$ where $x_i \gg x$. For example, a particle in an oscillator ground state may be near $-\infty$ and then on average appear at $+\infty$ in dt . This seems to be the interpretation if one uses $-\ln(\text{density})$ as Shannon's entropy.

A further issue with the $-W \ln(W)$ approach is that in the high energy limit, quantum density may be compared with a classical density given by $C/v(x)$ where $.5mv(x)v(x) + V(x) = E$. In the classical case, the particle is deterministic and follows a well defined path. It does not appear at one x at the middle of the trajectory and then suddenly at the end. The density $C/v(x)$ is proportional to dt the time spent in a fixed length dx . Fast speeds mean short times and possible difficulty of measurement i.e. the particle is moving by so fast it is missed by the measurer in some instances. If quantum mechanics matches this classical picture (by the correspondence principle) in the high energy limit, then $-\ln(\text{density})$ may also be calculated in this limit (as done in (2)). If that is the case, however, $\text{density} = P(x)$ which means that any path sequence $x_1 \ x_5 \ x_2 \ x_{25} \dots$ is possible, but that is not the case in the classical situation. Thus, we examine the classical scenario in more detail.

Classical Density and Probability

Consider a length L divided into fixed length intervals of dx with a classical bound state occurring over the length (with turning points). Deterministic motion occurs, but one may define a density (2) as $C/v(x)$ proportional to dt . This implies the probability to find the particle in dx at x is equal to $C/v(x)$ at that point. Thus, it is less likely to find a fast particle at x because it moves too quickly to be measured in some cases. This does not change the fact that the particle

moves past x because further measurements at $x_1 > x$ detect it. Nevertheless, one may argue that if the particle is not measured at x , one cannot prove it was there. Even accepting this, the particle does not appear at random positions at various t_i which are in sequence. I.e. $P(x) = C/v(x)$ cannot be applied to various scenarios: $x_1 x_2 x_5 x_4 x_3 x_6$ etc. The reason seems to be the following.

Consider a situation in which one has N identical bound systems of synchronized classical particles i.e. at t_i each particle is at the same x_i . There are N people taking measurements, one for each system. Because a $P(x)$ exists for each dx at x , one may detect the particle at x (denoted by 1) or not, denoted by 0. At t_i , each person is able to measure the entire length L and either find no result, or a position x of the particle. (As this is a classical system, one knows where the particle should be at t_i .) Thus, at t_i a certain number of 1 measurements are made for a specific x_i (because the particle is at x_i at this time). Call this number C_i . Continue this process taking M time measurements to obtain an augmented set of C_i , one for each dx interval. Different x_i have different C_i values. Dividing by MN yields C_i/MN together with $1 - C_i/MN$. These are the probabilities which describe the particle at each x_i . Thus, each dx interval has two probabilities and is independent of other dx intervals. This differs from the Shannon's entropy picture for which there are multiple outcomes for a specific trial, each with probability P_i . Here, we do not normalize C_i/MN over all x because they are not linked by probability. Unlike Shannon's case, where one knows $N P_i$ and can calculate the number of arrangements: $N! / \text{Product over } i N P_i$, here a specific outcome from one of the N people is not that same as another outcome in terms of probability i.e. counting.

For example, in one M trial, person 1 may find the following:

$X_1=0 \ x_2=1 \ x_3=1 \ x_4=0$ Probability = $[1 - C(x_1)/MN] \ C(x_2)/MN \ C(x_3)/MN \ [1 - C(x_4)/MN]$

Another person may find $X_1=1 \ x_2=1 \ x_3=1 \ x_4=1$ Probability = $C(x_1)/MN \ C(x_2)/MN \ C(x_3)/MN \ C(x_4)/MN$

The probabilities differ, thus the idea of taking the \ln of a combinatoric calculation does not apply. In Shannon's case, if outcome i does not occur, outcome j does. In the classical density situation, the particle is either found or not found at x (where it is supposed to be) at t_i . There are two probabilities for each $x - dx$ region. Furthermore, the particle is known to move from x_1 to x_2 to $x_3 \dots$ as repeated measurement shows. After many measurements, one does not establish a random scenario such as x_1 then x_5 etc.

As a result, we argue that taking the C_i 's and normalizing them such that:

$\text{Sum over } i \ C_i/B = 1$

and then C_i/B as $P(x)$ does not seem to have a physical foundation in the classical density case. We argue against the use of $-\text{density} \ln(\text{density})$ as entropy for this reason. If such a result holds for the classical case which is said to match the quantum one at high energy by the correspondence principle, it seems difficult to treat $P(x) = W(x)W(x)$ as a Shannon type probability.

(Alternatively, given that one knows classically where the particle should be at each t_i , one may attempt a measurement at the corresponding x_i . If the measurement detects the particle, one may record a 1 otherwise a 0. After N runs, one may count C_i for each dx about x_i . The idea is the same as above.)

Normalization of the Probability

In the classical case where density = $C/v(x)$, it seems one artificially normalizes $1/v(x)$ so that probabilities at different x values are linked. We argue that for each dx at x_i one has C_i/MN and $1-C_i/MN$ and these add to 1. There seems to be no reason to link the different x_i values. $1/v(x)$ is a relative probability. If it is large there is a high probability to measure the particle at a particular x , otherwise a low. One may choose a normalization for these relative probabilities i.e. Sum over $C/v(x) = 1$, but it does not mean that if the particle is not found at one x it is automatically at another (as in a Shannon's probability). If the particle is not found, we argue it means the measurement failed to detect it. The classical particle moves in a deterministic way and is at x no matter what. We argue that the quantum picture (which is an average one) also deals with points close to each other which is why $-1/2m d/dx d/dx W/W$ yields $KE(x)$ which is accurate for x and $x+dx$. The wavefunction is linked to the classical picture for all energy levels because $-1/2m d/dx d/dx W/W$ is equal to the classical kinetic energy regardless if the actual particle is moving in a stochastic manner and appearing at one place and then another. It seems that $P(x)$ does not measure this behaviour. What then does $P(x)$ measure? It is a physical observable and indicates that on average the particle may be found in certain regions and not others, but this is closely linked to internal interference i.e. $a(p)\cos(px)$ terms for $(a(p)=a(-p))$. Thus, density cancels at one place and adds at another. We argued in another note, that density canceling indicates motion opposite to average motion indicated by $-dV/dx$. Thus, quantum bound states seem to be similar to fluid flow (with $W(x)$ as the density) in the wavefunction -Schrodinger equation picture and not to a random motion scenario governed by $P(x)$. In other words, an average $P(x)$ does not necessarily mean random average x motion in time.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that $P(x)=W^*(x)W(x)$ in quantum mechanics does not seem to act like a Shannon's probability. For high energy, the quantum case should match the classical according to the correspondence principle. In the classical case, density equals $C/v(x)$, but the particle moves from x_1 to x_2 to x_3 etc. It does not jump from x_1 to x_{10} then back to x_3 etc. The density is proportional to dt i.e. the time the particle spends in a fixed length dx . If the particle moves quickly, it means that the probability of detecting it is low due to measurement issues. If it moves slowly, it is almost certain to be measured. Nevertheless, it moves in a fixed pattern - the classical particle is deterministic. We argue that in quantum mechanics, even though there are stochastic hits and a particle may jump from x_1 to x_{10} in a short time, on average (which we think is what the wavefunction measures), it moves from one x to another. The wavefunction is a sum of relative momentum probabilities at x and these probabilities already differ from the actual motion of the particle (they are probabilities). For example, the wavefunction is used to

calculate the average kinetic energy from one point to a nearby one. Thus, we argue that one may not use $P(x)$ as probability in the Shannon sense. In the Shannon scenario, the probability P_i represents a particular outcome. If one does not have one outcome, one has another. In the literature, $P(x)$ is employed in this manner for quantum mechanics, but we argue $W(x)W(x)$ is related to an average dynamic picture and should not.

Furthermore, in the classical case which matches the high energy quantum one, the scenario differs from Shannon's as we argue in this note. Thus, we suggest that there may be issues with the use of $-W*W \ln(W*W)$ in quantum mechanics. (In a previous note, we have suggested an alternative entropy density.)

References

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